

Fractional Order PID Based Coordinated Control Strategies for DG units in an Unbalanced Microgrid

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Abstract: In order to address voltage imbalance in a microgrid, this study outlines voltage and current management strategies based on fractional order PID for Distributed Generation (DG) units that use Voltage Source Converters (VSCs). The goal of these schemes is to achieve reference command control of the positive, negative, and zero sequence components of the Point of Common Coupling (PCC) voltage and the VSC currents individually and independently. To prevent overloading (in imbalanced settings) and asymmetrical errors, the present control systems' positive and negative sequence references include limitations that dynamically change. When it comes to microgrid operation, the active power control, frequency control, and reactive power-voltage droop control schemes determine the references of the positive sequence voltage control scheme. This is done to achieve the goal of using the same control schemes for both grid connected and islanded modes of operation, thus doing away with islanding detection. Two identical VSC-based DG units that provide electricity to the IEEE 34-node distribution network constructed in MATLAB were used to examine the performance of the different control strategies used to operate the VSC-based DG unit.

INTRODUCTION

DC power is generated by the majority of renewable energy sources (PV, FC, etc.), and it is also handled by the majority of storage systems (Battery, Supercapacitor, etc.). The AC Microgrid requires Voltage Source Converters (VSCs) to connect these energy generators and storage devices. Low voltage distribution networks known as AC microgrids often use Distributed Generation (DG) units to power local loads, which are inherently imbalanced [1]. Consequently, VSCs will often deliver imbalanced currents; selecting an appropriate control strategy is crucial to ensuring that VSC performance remains unaffected. Grid Connected and Islanded control methods provide additional difficulties when it comes to VSC control. In the Grid linked mode of operation, the Main Grid dictates the voltage and frequency of the microgrid. However, in the Standalone or Islanded modes of operation, the VSCs are responsible for setting these parameters. Hence, in the beginning, researchers suggested that VSCs running in the Grid linked and island modes of operation should have their own control systems [2]. To handle imbalanced loads, the similar idea was expanded upon in [3]. Nevertheless, switching between grid-connected and island modes of operation, and vice versa. The need for a quick and dependable islanding detection will be amply shown when the converse happens, leading to the forced switching of two sets of controllers. Since no approach is completely

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definitive, islanding detection remains a field of investigation. As a result, studies have started to suggest a unified control strategy that can be used to both the Grid-connected. The structure suggested in reference [4] is designed to manage the VSC in a synchronous manner, taking into consideration an assumed virtual inertia constant (H) and a virtual damping constant (KD). But overcurrents caused by grid failures will destroy the VSC switches. To remove the need for islanding detection, reference [5] developed a control method that is applicable to both grid-connected and island-only modes of operation, building on the concepts given in references [6] and [7]. Nevertheless, the findings do not clearly display the positive and negative sequence components of the voltages and currents, and the Grid linked and Islanded modes of operation have been examined independently. The control techniques mentioned in references 6, 7, and 11 work well when the system is balanced. However, when the loading is not balanced, the voltage at the Point of Common Coupling (PCC) becomes very distorted and imbalanced, which negatively impacts the VSC's performance. The control techniques given in references [6], [7] and [14] have been suggested appropriate adjustments to address this issue in references [12] - [14].

such that the PCC voltage remains balanced even when the load is unbalanced [11]. Zero Sequence Components have not been taken into account, nevertheless, since [12] only dealt with transformer windings linked to deltas and [13] only dealt with loads connected to deltas. However, in [14], the researchers kept the grid-connected and non-grid-connected systems under separate supervision.

many ways of doing things. In the cited works

of [15], [16], [18], [25], [26], [27], and [29] With the exception of [25], [26], voltage imbalance has been corrected in the indq-frame algorithm (no sequence components have been taken into account).

The signals that have been managed so far have a sinusoidal shape, but determining the boundaries of the present control loop references will be challenging because of this. The reference currents will become non-sinusoidal when a saturation block is used, particularly in fault circumstances, when the VSC is overloaded. Consequently, the following is the purpose of this paper:

objectives:

- To ensure that, regardless of load imbalance in the microgrid, the Line to Ground Voltages at the PCC of the VSCs remain balanced.
- To prevent damage to the VSC switches by limiting fault currents, particularly unsymmetrical faults.
- Both the grid-connected and island modes of operation should have the same control system.
- As a result, understanding the microgrid's dominant mode of operation becomes superfluous.

Along with the enhanced versions of the positive and negative sequence VSC current and PCC voltage control schemes (with regard to the control structures described in [13]), this study has also designed and implemented zero sequence VSC current and PCC voltage control techniques. Some of the enhancements to the positive and negative sequence VSC current and PCC voltage control methods include taking frequency variation into account in the feed forward terms and including dynamically variable limitations into both the PCC and the VSC.

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therefore leading to enhanced transient performance, and the VSC current control architecture. So, the PCC Voltage and the VSC current's positive, negative, and zero sequence components will be managed autonomously. The VSC current control techniques have been designed to prevent overloading in imbalanced situations and asymmetrical faults by dynamically adjusting the limits for the positive and negative sequence references. In order to achieve the goal of keeping the PCC voltage balanced at all times, the references for the Negative and Zero Sequence PCC Voltage control schemes have been set to '0.' The references for the Positive Sequence voltage control scheme will be determined by the Active Power Control, Frequency Control, and Reactive Power-Voltage droop control schemes that are presented in [5]. Figure 1 shows the updated IEEE 34 node distribution network, and Figure 1(b) shows the results of testing the control methods on two VSC based DG units that provide electricity to the network. The remainder of the document is structured as follows. An overview of a VSC-based DG unit, complete with PV array and BESS, was given in Section II. Section III introduced the many control methods that may be used to manage the VSC and the Buck-Boost converters. Section IV presents the simulation findings that prove the control techniques given in this study are effective. To wrap up the paper, we have Section V.

I. SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

Fig. 1 Modified IEEE 34 Node Distribution Network. A three phase three level Neutral Point Clamped (NPC) converter acts as a VSC and is connected to the microgrid through a three phase LC filter and a three phase coupling transformer (Both the

primary and secondary windings of the coupling transformer are Y-connected and

Fig 1:Modified IEEE 34 Node Distribution Network.

the neutral point is grounded). Two BESS banks (represented by the Thevenin's equivalent model which is slightly different from the model presented in [19]) are connected in parallel to the DC link capacitors (C1 and C2). Two identical PV arrays (represented by the Norton's equivalent model [20], [21]) are connected to the DC link capacitors (C1 and C2) through two Buckboost converters. The Buck-boost converters operate in such a manner that the PV arrays always deliver power at the Maximum Power Point (MPP). The VSC supplies power to the microgrid according to the reference command (when the microgrid is in the grid connected mode of operation) or according to the load demand (when the microgrid is in the islanded mode of operation). The BESS banks take care of the mismatch between the power generated by the PV array and the power supplied by the VSC (The BESS banks will either get charged or discharged depending on the direction of flow of current through the BESS banks). Two identical VSC based DG units are connected at nodes '850' and '832' of the modified IEEE 34 node distribution network shown in Fig. 1. Fig. 2 shows the representation of the improved version of the SRF-PLL [9], [10] and the objective of this PLL is to synchronize the dq-frame with the positive sequence component of the voltage at the

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PCC (that is the converter side of the coupling transformer as shown Fig.1

Fig:2 Improved SRF-PLL

II. CONTROL STRATEGY

This paper mainly focuses on improvement of non-linear power damping controller to integrate VSC's to weak grids. Fig.1 shows the grid connected VSC supplying a local load. It has linear power-damping/ synchronizing controller and non-linear

power damping controller. Fig.3 shows the linear control structure. Fig.4 shows non-linear control structure. Also, it has a voltage

amplitude controller which provides specific control depending on type of bus. It provides different control strategy for output voltage to PV and PQ bus. It is shown in Fig.6. The angle and frequency loops provide synchronizing and damping power components for the VSC to track frequency and angle deviations of the grid and automatically synchronizes with grid. Depending on the frequency error only the reference of the load angle is found and the real power reference is obtained as the function of load angle error. The reference frequency (ω_{set}) in the frequency loop is set

equal to the grid frequency and the VSC gives the reference power (P_{set}) in steady state conditions. The transferred real power is given by

$$P = \frac{E}{R^2 + X^2} (XV_L \sin\delta + R(E - V_L \cos\delta)). \tag{1}$$

Modelling & control topics by utilizing idea of fractional order systems have been drawing more interest in current days. FOPID controller [17] is an appropriate fractional order structure that has been implemented for control purposes. It is a generalized type of conventional PID controller. In this controller, derivative and integrator parts have non-integer orders and so the order should be determined by designer. As a result, the controller would have five parameters to be determined. The mathematical representation of FOPID controller is like

$$C(t) = K_p * e(t) + K_I \int e(t) (dt)^\lambda + K_D \frac{d^\mu e(t)}{dt} \tag{2}$$

λ is the order of the integral term (I) and μ is the order of the derivative term (D) of FOPID controller. From equation (2), it is notable that two extra parameters are to be set for the control action than conventional PID controller. Here, if $\lambda = 1$ and $\mu = 1$ the conventional PID controller will be obtained. Also, if $\lambda = 1$ and $\mu = 0$ the conventional PI, if $\lambda = 0$, $\mu = 1$ the conventional PD and if $\lambda = 0$, $\mu = 0$ the standard proportional (P) controller will be obtained. So, all sort of PID controller are

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distinctive cases of FOPID controller. Therefore, design parameters in FOPID controller are K_P , K_I , K_D , λ and μ need

for a PLL in steady-state operation and several transient conditions.

Fig.3. Linear control scheme.

Fig.4. Non-linear supplementary control structure.

III. SYSTEM MODELING

To assess the dynamic performance of the system on a weak grid, this section presents a small-signal stability study of a grid-connected VSC. A converter and controller, an RL filter, a connecting line, and an infinite grid are all components of a three-phase power system. If the VSC were perfect, the VSC local

voltage is equal to the controller command, thus it is possible to model the VSC and

PWM blocks using a voltage-average method. Table I provides the system parameters. Here is how to build the VSC and its controller enhanced model. To begin, we have the dynamic equation for the load angle, which is

$$\Delta\delta = \Delta w \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

$$\Delta P = \frac{\partial P}{\partial \delta} \Delta\delta + \frac{\partial P}{\partial E_F} \Delta E_F \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

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Fig.5. Control topologies for output voltage control. (a) P-V bus control. (b) P-Q bus control strategy.

The voltage loop dynamic equation is given by

$$\Delta E = -w \Delta E + w \Delta v - w K \Delta E \quad (5)$$

$$\Delta \dot{v} = -K_{vi} \Delta E_F \quad (6)$$

Where v is the output of the integrator K_{vi} , and E_F is the filter voltage amplitude expressed by

$$\Delta E_F = \frac{E_{Fd0} \Delta E_{Fd} + E_{Fq0} \Delta E_{Fq}}{E_{F0}} \pi r^2 \quad (7)$$

$$\Delta E = L \frac{d\Delta i_d}{dt} + R \Delta i_d - w L \Delta i_q \quad (8)$$

$$\Delta E_{Fq} = L_c \frac{d\Delta i_q}{dt} + R_c \Delta i_d + w_0 L_c \Delta i_d \quad (9)$$

The currents dynamics in the dq reference- frame are given by

$$\frac{d\Delta i_d}{dt} = \frac{1}{L} (-E \sin \delta \Delta \delta + \Delta E \cos \delta - R \Delta i_d + w_0 L_c \Delta i_q) \quad (10)$$

$$\frac{d\Delta i_q}{dt} = \frac{1}{L} (-E_0 \cos \delta_0 \Delta \delta + \Delta E \sin \delta_0 - R \Delta i_q - w_0 L_c \Delta i_d) \quad (11)$$

The overall system model is

$$x_1 = x_2 \quad (12)$$

$$x_2 = a_1 x_1 + a_2 x_2 + a_3 x_3 \quad (13)$$

$$\dot{x} = u + E \frac{V_L}{X} \cos x - w x \quad (14)$$

Where $a_1 = -K_p K_d$, $a_2 = -K_p K_i K_d$ and $a_3 = -K_p$, and

$[x_1, x_2, x_3] = [\Delta \delta, \Delta \omega, \Delta P]$. u_f is defined as $u_f = (u \omega_c V_L \sin x_1) / X$, where u is the control input.

The control objective is to ensure the

convergence of the error $e_i = x_i - x_{i,ref}$ to zero. The first step is to stabilize δ , thus the Lyapunov function

$$V_1 = \frac{1}{2} x_1^2 \quad (15)$$

is defined and the reference of frequency deviation value and V_1 are given by

$$x_{2ref} = -K x_1 K > 0 \quad (16)$$

$$\dot{V}_1 = -K_1 x_1 + x_1 e_2$$

(21) In the next step, the Lyapunov function is

defined as $V_2 = V_1 + 1/2 e^2$ and x_{3ref} is

$$x_{3ref} = c_1 x_1 + c_2 e_2 \quad (17)$$

$$\text{Where } C_1 = \frac{(1 - k_1(-a_2 + k_1) + a_1)}{a_3} \quad (18)$$

$$C_2 = -\frac{(k_1 + k_2 + a_2)}{a_3}, k_2 > 0 \quad (19)$$

CONTROLLER PARAMETERS

Kp	Ki	Kd	λ	μ
11.98	10.85	11.44	1.29	0.02

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Table 1: Circuit Parameters of each DG unit

PV Array	Capacity	2300KW($n_s=48, n_p=240$)
	Open Circuit voltage(V_{oc})	36 V(for each module)
	Short Circuit Current(I_{sc})	8.44 A(for each module)
	Voltage at MPP(V_{MPP})	26.74V(for each module)
	Current at MPP(I_{MPP})	7.65A(for each module)
Buck boost converter	L_{dc1}, L_{dc2}	10mH, 10mH
	C_{dc1}, C_{dc2}	20mF, 20mF
Battery Energy Storage System	Rated Voltage	725 V in each pole
	$R_{self_Discharge1}, R_{self_Discharge2}$	∞, ∞
	$C_{capacity1}, C_{capacity2}$	2970000 F, 2970000 F
	$R_{series1}, R_{series2}$	0.0158 Ω , 0.0158 Ω
	$R_{transient_s1}, R_{transient_s2}$	0.00354 Ω , 0.00354 Ω
	$C_{transient_s1}, C_{transient_s2}$	3316.9 F, 3316.9 F
	$R_{transient_L1}, R_{transient_L2}$	0.01056 Ω , 0.01056 Ω
	$C_{transient_L1}, C_{transient_L2}$	21096.4 F, 21096.4 F
Voltage Source Converter	Rated Current(I_{rated})	2000A(rms)
	DC Capacitors($C1, C2$)	200mF, 200mF
	R_{loss1}, R_{loss2}	∞, ∞
	IGBT ON Resistance	0.5 m Ω
	Filter Inductor	$R_f=0\Omega, L_f=300\mu H$
	Filter Capacitor(C_f)	400 μF
Coupling Transformer	Voltage Ratio	480/24900 V
	KVA Rating	1650 KVA
	Base Frequency	60 HZ
	Winding Type	Y-Gr/Y-Gr
	Leakage Resistance	0.1 pu

and following the approach presented and , it can be shown that the stability of the overall system is confirmed if

$$\begin{aligned}
 u &= (A + k \frac{EV_L}{X} \cos x) x \\
 f &= 1 X \frac{1}{X} + (B + \frac{EV_L}{X} \cos x_1 - a_3) e_2 \\
 &+ \dots \dots \dots (C \\
 &- k_3)e_3 \quad k_3 > 0 \\
 &\dots \dots \dots (20)
 \end{aligned}$$

Where

$$A = K_f - k^2 K_f + k_1 K_d K_f - 2k_1 K_p +$$

$$\frac{k_1^3}{K_p} - \frac{k_2}{K_p} \quad (21)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 B &= (k_1 + k_2 - K_d) K_f + \\
 &\frac{1}{1 - k^2 - k^2 - k_1 k_2} \\
 &\frac{1}{K_p} \quad (22)
 \end{aligned}$$

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

The MATLAB/SIMULINK model depicts the microgrid-like modified IEEE 34-node distribution network (Fig. 1) that receives electricity from two identical VSC-based DG units. By removing the voltage regulators that were previously part of the network, we can test how well the VSCs can improve the feeder's voltage profile without those unnecessary components. Table I contains the parameters of the DG units and compensators, while Table 8 has the data of the IEEE 34 node distribution network. Both VSCs use a reference command of 1150 kW for the Active Power Control loop, while the rated capacity of the PV array in each DG unit is 2300 kW at STC. Section A: Switching from Grid-Connected to Islanded Mode of Operation: The microgrid was operating in the Grid Connected mode of operation. The PV arrays of both the DG units were operating at the Maximum Power Point (MPP) at STC

and were generating 2300 kW each. Both

the VSCs were supplying 1150 kW to the microgrid (VSC-1 was supplying around 200 kVAR and VSC-2 was supplying

around 320 kVAR to the microgrid). The microgrid was supplying around 450 kW and 150 kVAR to the main grid as shown in Fig. 5b (due to the fact that the power supplied by the VSCs to the microgrid is more than the power consumed by the load in the microgrid). Suddenly at $t=0.75s$, the

circuit breaker 'BRK' has been opened.

(a)

(e)

(b)

(f)

(c)

(g)

(d)

(h)

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Fig. 5: Transition from the Grid Connected mode of Operation to the Islanded mode of Operation.

Based on the results presented in Fig. 5, it is clear that the controllers were able to control the voltage and frequency of the VSCs (and ultimately the microgrid) within the nominal operating range, therefore the microgrid has come to a steady operating point without any large excursions in the voltage and frequency (Fig. 5d and 5e shows that there is a temporary overvoltage for a very short duration and the voltages immediately come to steady state). Since the Active Power supplied by both the VSCs now is less than the reference command of 1150 kW (which can be observed in Fig. 5i for VSC-1; not shown for VSC-2 due to brevity), the FOPI controllers of the Active Power control loops of both the VSCs have now become saturated and the droop control schemes have taken charge in deciding the frequency of both the VSCs (which ultimately will decide the frequency of the microgrid). Fig. 5f shows the variation in the frequency of VSC-1 (The variation in the frequency of VSC-2 is similar to that of the frequency of VSC-1 which hasn't been shown due to brevity). From Fig. 5h it is clear that the BESS has taken care of the difference between the power generated by the PV array and the power supplied by the VSC (the results have been shown for VSC-1). The same observation is true of VSC-2 as well (which hasn't been shown due to

brevity). Fig. 5g shows the Line currents supplied by VSC-1.

Table.2: Comparing the results with results in paper[30], is shown below.

s.no	content	PI	FOPID
1	dP	100kw	40kw
2	dQ	100kvar	40kvar
3	dP battery dc side	200kw	98kw
4	dQ vsc1 dc side	190Kw	97kw
5	dP VSC-1 to micro grid	120kw	55kw
6	dQ VSC-1 to micro grid	36kvar	14kvar

B. Islanded mode of operation–Response to Sudden Change in Load:

The microgrid was operating in the Islanded mode of operation. Suddenly at $t=1.0s$, the load has been changed as follows and restored to the original loading condition at $t=1.5s$:

- The load between Phase 'b' and 'n' and Phase 'c' and 'n' have been temporarily switched off for the Y-connected spot load at node – 844.
- All the Y-connected distributed loads between Phase 'b' and 'n' and Phase 'c' and 'n' have been temporarily switched off.
- The Y-connected distributed load between nodes – 820 and 822, connected between Phase 'a' and 'n' has been temporarily doubled.
- All the delta-connected distributed loads between Phases 'b' and 'c' have been temporarily switched off.

- 1) Zero Sequence VSC Current Control and PCC Voltage Control are disabled [13]: From Fig. 6d it can be clearly understood that the Line to

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Neutral voltages at the PCC are severely unbalanced, while the Line to Line Voltages (shown in Fig. 6e) are balanced which clearly indicates that the Negative sequence components are absent and the Zero Sequence Components are present. Therefore, the Y-connected loads will experience severe voltage unbalance; clearly indicating the need for zero sequence voltage compensation. Since the Line to Neutral voltages at the PCC is unbalanced, the Line to Neutral voltages at node – 862.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

Fig. 6: Islanded mode of operation– Response to Sudden Change in Load graphs that are shown in Fig. 6a will be much more severely unbalanced due to the fact that the voltage drops across the feeders are unbalanced due to unbalanced currents flowing in the feeders. However, the severity of unbalance in the Line to Line voltage is much lesser (shown in Fig. 6b) due to the fact that the Zero Sequence components are absent in the line to Line Voltages. Fig. 6f show the variations in the Active and Reactive Power supplied by VSC-1 to the microgrid. Fig. 6c shows the

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variation in the currents supplied by VSC-1. Results have been presented only for the reduction in load (and have not been shown for the restoration of the load) due to brevity. Table.3:Comparing results with [30],is as shown below

S.no	Content	PI	FOPI D
1	line currents of VSC-1	0.76 pu	0.62pu
2	dV	1.2pu	1.12pu
3	P from VSC-1 to MG	680kw	740kw
4	Q from VSC-1 to MG	0kvar	6kvar

C. Islanded mode of operation–Response to Single Line to Ground Fault:

The microgrid was operating in the Islanded mode of operation. Suddenly at $t=1.0s$, a temporary single line to ground fault has occurred at node – 830 for a duration of 0.12s (shown in Fig. 7a). The result in Fig. 8c clearly indicates that the

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

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Fig.7: Islanded mode of operation-Response to Single Line to Ground Fault.

fault current has been limited to less than 1.0pu which clearly indicates the advantage of using dynamically varying limits for the references of the positive and negative sequence current control loops. The current controllers were capable of controlling the currents to the reference commands for VSC-1. During the transient period, there will be a peak overshoot due to the fact that the closed loop current control is not a first order system (It is a Third order system). After the fault was cleared, the results clearly show that the PCC Voltage controllers were capable of regulating the voltages to the reference commands (Fig. 7b shows the PCC voltage at VSC-1 in abc- frame). From Fig. 7e it is clear that the PV array still operates at MPP even during the fault condition. Since the VSC effectively doesn't supply power to the microgrid during the fault, all the power generated by the PV array flows into the BESS (the

results have been shown for VSC-1). Fig. 7d and 7g respectively show the ratio of the Negative and Zero Sequence components of the Line current of VSC-1 with respect to the Positive Sequence component. Table.4: Comparing the results with [30], as shown below

S.no	Content	PI	FOPID
1	Line currents of vsc-1	1.3pu	0.75pu
2	Fault current	4pu	2.4pu

V. CONCLUSION

Effective integration of VSCs to modified IEEE34 Bus systems is made possible in this work by presenting a novel control architecture. The suggested FOPID-based coordinated controller may improve system performance in these instances since they are classified as large-signal disturbances.

In addition, the controller may function in extremely grid outage and restoration circumstances. The current control strategy has been suggested to use dynamically variable limits, which have been instrumental in bringing the fault current down to less than 1.0pu. By successfully regulating the PCC voltage and VSC current to their respective reference instructions during grid breakdown and operation restoration, the VSC based DG unit was able to handle imbalanced circumstances. For optimal performance, use the FOPID controller. Even under imbalanced conditions, the FOPID controller allows for a superior reaction. We used MATLAB/SIMULINK to build and test the control schemes, compensation results, and dependability for the proposed system.

REFERENCES

- [1] Nikos Hatziaargyriou, "Microgrids Architectures and Control," IEEE press, John Wiley and Sons, 2014.
- [2] H. Karimi, H. Nikkhajoei, R. Iravani, "Control of an Electronically-Coupled Distributed Resource Unit Subsequent to an Islanding Event," IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery, vol. 23, no. 1, pp. 493–501, Jan 2008.
- [3] H. Karimi, A. Yazdani, R. Iravani, "Robust Control of an Autonomous Four Wire Electronically-Coupled Distributed Generation Unit," IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery, vol. 26, no. 1, pp. 455–466, Jan 2011.
- [4] F. Gao, R. Iravani, "A Control Strategy for a Distributed Generation Unit in Grid- Connected and Autonomous Modes of Operation," IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery, Vol 23, No 2, pp 850–859, Apr 2008.
- [5] M. B. Delghavi, A. Yazdani, "A Unified Control Strategy for Electronically Interfaced Distributed Energy Resources," IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery, vol. 27, no. 2, pp. 803–812, Apr 2012.
- [6] A. Yazdani, "Control of an Islanded Distributed Energy Resource Unit with Load Compensating Feed-Forward," IEEE Power Engineering Society General Meeting, 7 pp. July 20–24, 2008.
- [7] M. B. Delghavi and A. Yazdani, "A Control Strategy for Islanded Operation of a Distributed Resource (DR) Unit," IEEE Power and Energy Society General Meeting, 8 pp. July 26–30, 2009.
- [8] IEEE PES Distribution System Analysis Subcommittee Radial Test Feeders. [Online]. Available: <http://ewh.ieee.org/soc/pes/dsacom/testfeeders/index.html>.
- [9] A. Yazdani, R. Iravani, "A Unified Dynamic Model and Control for the Voltage- Sourced Converter Under Unbalanced Grid Conditions," IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery, vol. 21, no. 3, pp. 1620–1629, Jul 2006.
- [10] A. Yazdani, "Modelling and Control of the Three-Level Neutral Point Diode Clamped (NPC) Converter for High-Power Applications," Ph.D. dissertation, Univ. Toronto, Toronto, ON, Canada, 2005.
- [11] N. Pogaku, M. Prodanovic, T. C. Green, "Modeling, Analysis and Testing of Autonomous Operation of an Inverter-Based Microgrid," IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics, Vol 22, No 2, pp 613–625, Mar 2007.
- [12] M. B. Delghavi, A. Yazdani, "Islanded-Mode Control of Electronically Coupled Distributed-Resource Units Under Unbalanced and Nonlinear Load Conditions," IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery, vol. 26, no. 2, pp. 661–673, Apr 2011.
- [13] N. R. Merritt, C. Chakraborty, P. Bajpai, "A Control Strategy for Islanded Operation of a Voltage Source Converter (VSC) Based Distributed Resource Unit under Unbalanced Conditions," IEEE International Conference on Industrial Informatics (INDIN), pp. 1550–1555, July 22– 24, 2015.
- [14] M. Kumar, S. C. Srivastava, S. N. Singh, "Control Strategies of a DC Microgrid for Grid Connected and Islanded Operations," IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 1588–1601, July 2015.
- [15] M. Savaghebi, A. Jalilian, J. C. Vasquez, J. M. Guerrero, "Secondary Control Scheme for Voltage Unbalance Compensation in an Islanded Droop-Controlled Microgrid," IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid, Vol 3, No 2, pp 797 807, June 2012.
- [16] M. Savaghebi, A. Jalilian, J. C. Vasquez, J. M. Guerrero, "Autonomous Voltage Unbalance Compensation in an Islanded Droop-Controlled Microgrid," IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics, vol. 60, no. 4, pp. 1390–1402, Apr 2013.
- [17] jun-yi-cao, jinliang, bing-gang cao, 'Optimization Of Fractional Order PID Controllers Based On Genetic Algorithm' 4th International Conference on Machine Learning and Cybernetics, Guangzhou, 18-21, August 2015.
- [18] Mohsen Hamzeh, H. Karimi, H. Mokhtari, "A New Control Strategy for a Multi- Bus MV Microgrid Under Unbalanced Conditions," IEEE Transactions on Power Systems, vol. 27, no. 4, pp. 2225–2232, Nov 2012.
- [19] M. Chen, G. A. Rincon-Mora, "Accurate Electrical Battery Model Capable of Predicting Runtime and IV Performance," IEEE Transactions on Energy Conversion, vol. 21, no. 2, pp. 504–511, June 2006.
- [20] M. G. Villalva, J. R. Gazoli, E. R. Filho, "Comprehensive Approach to Modeling and Simulation of Photovoltaic Arrays," IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics, vol. 24, no. 5, pp. 1198–1208, May 2009.
- [21] Y. A. Mahmoud, W. Xiao, H. H. Zeineldin, "A Parameterization Approach for Enhancing PV Model Accuracy," IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics, vol. 60, no. 12, pp. 5708–5716, Dec 2013.
- [22] A. K. Abdelsalam, A. M. Massoud, S. Ahmed, P. N. Enjeti, "High-Performance Adaptive Perturb and Observe MPPT Technique for Photovoltaic-Based Microgrids," IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics, vol. 26, no. 4, pp. 1010–1021, Apr 2011.
- [23] S. B. Kjaer, "Evaluation of the 'Hill Climbing' and the 'Incremental Conductance' Maximum Power Point Trackers for Photovoltaic Power Systems," IEEE Transactions on Energy Conversion, vol. 27, no. 4, pp. 922–929, Dec 2012.
- [24] D. Sera, L. Mathe, T. Kerekes, S.V. Spataru, R. Teodorescu, "On the Perturb-and- Observe and Incremental Conductance MPPT Methods for PV Systems," IEEE Journal of Photovoltaics, vol. 3, no. 3, pp. 1070–1078, Jul 2013.
- [25] Y. Li, D. M. Vilathgamuwa, P. C. Loh, "Microgrid power quality enhancement using a three-phase four-wire grid-interfacing compensator," IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications, vol. 41, no. 6, pp. 1707-1719, Nov/Dec. 2005.
- [26] Fen Tang, Xiao Zhou, Lexuan Meng, J. M. Guerrero, J. C. Vasquez, "Secondary voltage unbalance compensation for three-phase four-wire islanded microgrids," International Multi-Conference on Systems, Signals & Devices (SSD), Barcelona, 2014, pp. 1-5.
- [27] A. Camacho, M. Castilla, J. Miret, A. Borrell, L. G. de Vicua, "Active and Reactive Power Strategies With Peak Current Limitation for Distributed Generation Inverters During Unbalanced Grid Faults," IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics, vol.

62, no. 3, pp. 1515-1525, Mar 2015.

[28] N. R. Tummuru, M. K. Mishra, S. Srinivas, "An Improved Current Controller for Grid Connected Voltage Source Converter in Microgrid Applications," IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Energy, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 595-605, Apr 2015.

[29] L. Meng, X. Zhao, F. Tang, M. Savaghebi, T. Dragicevic, J. C. Vasquez, J. M. Guerrero, "Distributed Voltage Unbalance Compensation in Islanded Microgrids by Using a Dynamic Consensus Algorithm," IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics, vol. 31, no. 1, pp. 827-838, Jan 2016.